

STUDIES ON THE METAL COMPLEXES OF HYDROXAMIC ACIDS. PART V. CO-DETERMINATION OF IRON AND MANGANESE WITH ANTHRANILOHYDROXAMIC ACID

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Anthranilohydroxamic acid (2-aminobenzohydroxamic acid) has been studied as a colorimetric reagent for co-determination of iron and manganese. Iron (ferric or ferrous) has been estimated by measuring the optical density of the orange-red complex (λ_{max} 450 m μ) extracted from aqueous medium at pH 4.5 with butyl alcohol. Manganese is then determined in the aqueous layer with the same reagent at pH above 9.2, when a wine-red complex (λ_{max} 490-500 m μ) is formed. A smooth separation and co-determination of iron and manganese have thus been possible. An amount of iron, as high as 250 times that of the manganese, does not offer any difficulty.

Nicotino- and isonicotinohydroxamic acids have been recommended by the author (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 311) as sensitive and useful reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of manganese by making use of the red-violet complex formed at or above pH 9. Interference due to copper, cobalt, nickel and silver was eliminated by the careful addition of sodium cyanide. However, the method failed in the presence of iron as iron developed with these reagents at or above pH 4 a strong golden yellow colour, which persisted even in the alkaline range. The iron complexes in these cases were found to be only partially extractable with higher alcohols. Picolino- and quinaldino-hydroxamic acids (Dutta, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 339), on the other hand, formed easily extractable iron complexes, but produced no suitable colour reaction with manganese. A satisfactory separation and simultaneous determination of iron and manganese were therefore not possible with any one of these pyridino- or quinolino-hydroxamic acids.

A study of anthranilo-(2-aminobenzohydroxamic acid) has now been made in an effort to examine the modifications in properties which might result from the substitution of the acidic OH group of salicylohydroxamic acid (Ray and Bhaduri, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 164, 103) by a basic NH₂ group. The notable modification in its properties over those of salicylohydroxamic acid was the formation of the wine-red manganese complex in alkaline medium. Salicylohydroxamic acid produced under similar conditions a greenish brown colour. Anthranilohydroxamic acid produces with ferric or ferrous iron an orange-red coloured complex above pH 4. The complex can be readily extracted with higher alcohols at pH 4 to 7. In the mixture containing iron (ferric or ferrous) and manganese, excess reagent is added, pH adjusted to 4-5 and the iron complex extracted with butyl alcohol, and the optical density measured at 450 m μ . In the aqueous layer, pH is brought to above 9 and after shaking and keeping for a few minutes, the optical density of the wine-red colour is determined at 490-500 m μ .

A satisfactory separation and estimation of iron and manganese in a mixture have thus been possible. Even a large amount of iron, as high as 250 times that of manganese, does not pose any problem.

The reagent, anthranilohydroxamic acid, is prepared by the interaction of hydroxylamine and methylanthranilate. Preparation of this reagent is simpler than that of the pyridinohydroxamic acids as in the present case the ester, methyl anthranilate, is a readily available commercial product.

EXPERIMENTAL

Scott and Wood (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 515) prepared anthranilohydroxamic acid by the interaction of hydroxylamine and methylanthranilate in aqueous alcoholic medium. The reaction was found to be very slow and it was therefore modified.

Sodium Salt of Anthranilohydroxamic Acid.—Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (35 g.) was treated in ethyl alcoholic medium with sodium ethoxide (11.5 g. sodium) under mechanical stirring. After 2 hours, the precipitated sodium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate treated with methylanthranilate (35 g.). After an hour's stirring more sodium ethoxide (5 g. sodium) was added and stirring continued for 3 hours. The mixture was then cooled and the sodium salt of the anthranilohydroxamic acid filtered. It was purified by dissolving it in the minimum amount of hot water and then reprecipitating it in the cold with the aid of an equal volume of acetone. The substance forms shining colorless crystals, highly soluble in water, yield 12 g. (Found: Na, 11.82; H₂O, 10.12. C₇H₇O₂Na.H₂O requires Na, 11.97 H₂O, 9.37%). [Found (anhydrous compound): N, 15.71. C₇H₇O₂N₂Na requires N, 16.09%]. It responds to all the usual reactions of hydroxamic acid. Its colour reactions towards vanadium, iron, manganese and molybdenum were highly sensitive. An aqueous solution (1-4%) of the reagent was prepared in water. The stronger solutions were used when the mixture to be analysed contained a considerable amount of iron.

Determination of Iron.—Ferric or ferrous iron was determined by measuring the optical density of the orange-red complex formed in aqueous medium between iron and the reagent, at $\lambda_{\max}$ 450 m μ within the pH range 4 to 7. Alternatively, the coloured complex was extracted out of the aqueous medium (pH as above) by butyl alcohol and the measurement made at $\lambda_{\max}$ 450 m μ against the same solvent. Beer's law was obeyed (Sandell sensitivity 0.014 γ). Vanadium interferes seriously. As with other hydroxamic acids (*loc. cit.*) in presence of small amounts of Ti, U or Mo, measurements are to be made at 500 m μ .

Determination of Manganese.—The manganese solution was treated with an excess reagent, pH adjusted to above 9.2 with ammonia, and the solution shaken for a few minutes, when a wine-red colour developed. Optical density was measured at 490-500 m μ . Beer's law was followed (Sandell sensitivity 0.013 γ). Interference due to copper, nickel and cobalt was eliminated by the careful addition of sodium cyanide, followed by the reagent and ammonia and measuring the optical density after 30 minutes of the addition of the reagent. In presence of moderate amounts of vanadium and molybdenum and small amounts of titanium and uranium, excess ammonia was used, and the colour measured at 550 m μ .

Determination of Iron and Manganese in presence of one another.—Excess reagent was added to the mixture containing iron and manganese (a total of 15 c.c. of 4%

reagent solution being used for a mixture containing 25.6 mg. of Fe and 0.2 mg. of Mn) and the pH of the solution (volume about 20-40 c.c.) was now adjusted approximately to 4-5 (pH paper). The red-coloured complex, which remained in solution when the iron content was below 2 mg. (or else precipitated out of the solution), was then extracted with butyl^l alcohol. For a total iron content of 25.6 mg., four extractions (8 c.c. each) were sufficient. The extracts were collected and volume made up to 25 or 50 c.c., depending on the amount of the iron. In the case of a strong colour an aliquot from this extract was further diluted with butyl^l alcohol and finally the optical density measured at 450 m μ in a cell of suitable thickness (1 cm or 0.5 cm cell). From a knowledge of the Beer's law curve of iron, the amount present in the sample was evaluated.

FIG. 1

Beer's law curves.

The aqueous extract was then transferred to a 25 or 50 c.c. flask, a few c.c. more of the reagent were added, if required, the medium was made ammoniacal, the solution shaken for a few minutes, and the manganese content determined from the O.D. measured at 490-500 m μ (1 cm cell). Results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Determination of iron and manganese by anthranilhydroxamic acid.

Fe present (total). 0.200 (Fe ³⁺) mg.	Mn present (total). 0.200 mg.	Fe found. 0.206 mg.	Mn found. 0.202 mg.
0.400	0.100	0.402	0.102
0.800	0.100	0.795	0.104
1.600	0.100	1.620	0.097
3.200	0.100	3.220	0.104
6.400	0.100	6.410	0.103
12.800	0.100	12.800	0.102
25.600	0.100	25.800	0.104
2.00 (Fe ²⁺)	0.100	2.08	0.102
2.00	0.200	2.10	0.206

The reagent was also found suitable for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium. In 1:1 alcohol (ethyl) medium, traces of vanadium produce at pH 3 to 4 a red colour ($\lambda_{\max}$ 460-470m μ). The coloured complex in aqueous medium at pH 3 to 4 is bluish purple and can easily be extracted out with butyl alcohol and optical density of the red coloured extract measured at 460-470 m μ . Beer's law was found to hold and Sandell sensitivity worked out to be .013 γ .

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